

Assessment of Entrepreneurship Education Knowledge Acquisition, Change of Attitude to Entrepreneurship and Skills Acquisition in Entrepreneurship Among University Undergraduates in South-Western Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study was designed to evaluate the entrepreneurship education knowledge change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship among university undergraduates in South-west Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Three states were randomly selected from Southwest, Nigeria from which one public and one private university each were randomly selected. The instruments used were Entrepreneurship Education Students Achievement Test and Undergraduate's entrepreneurial and Management Competence Questionnaire which yielded reliability coefficient of 0.81 and 0.72 respectively. Paired and independent t-test was used to analyse the data collected at 0.05 level of significance. The pre

and post test scores on undergraduates entrepreneurship education knowledge (tc1819) = 337.26 change of attitude to Entrepreneurship (tc1819) = 240.80 and skills acquisition in Entrepreneurship (tc1819) = 123.05 indicated the positive impact of entrepreneurship education significant differences were also observed between the public and private undergraduates' Entrepreneurship education knowledge (tc1819) = 5.46, change of attitude to Entrepreneurship (tc1819) = 4.96 and skills acquisition in Entrepreneurship (tc1819) = 4.20. Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made among which are: University lecturers should demonstrate a strong dedication to the teaching of entrepreneurship education general studies Government, non-governmental organizations and philanthropists should assist in providing sufficient resources for the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education general studies course, the Vice Chancellors in Public Universities to intensify more efforts on effective implementation of entrepreneurship education general studies course.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial knowledge, attitude to entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship skills, university undergraduates.*

Introduction

Nigeria like most developing nations of the world is faced with different problems ranging

from poverty, unemployment, ethno-religious conflicts, to diseases among others (Olise, 2011). This situation according to him pose great

challenges to the very existence of individual in most developing nations thereby calling for the training of educated men and women who can function effectively in the society in which they live. Nigeria therefore need enterprising individual in a way that will bring substantial reduction of unemployment and job creation (Cooney, 2009 and Aladekimo, 2004).

In an attempt to redirect unemployed youths to productive activities upon graduation from universities, the Federal Government in 2006, though the National University commission introduced entrepreneurship education into the university academic curriculum in order to stem the ever rising hike of unemployment and achieve appreciable success in employment generation (NUC, 2011).

Stakeholder in education have constantly lamented the unfortunate trend in which tertiary institutions annually turn out graduates who roam our street daily in search for job opportunities and the inability of Nigeria education system to produce graduates who can create job and be self-reliant.

In a posture reaction to the development, Arogundade (2011) opined that Federal government in 2006 revised the curriculum of university education to include entrepreneurship education in order to equip the Nigerian graduates in effort to reduce the growing unemployment and to create more jobs as well as wealth.

Entrepreneurship education according to Egai (2009) is a deliberately planned process of action that are aimed of transforming culture, enterprise creation and expansion and subsequently creating employment for young men and women. To Agbonlohor (2010) Entrepreneurship education is central to the economic development of nations. Therefore, introduction of entrepreneurial education as one of the course in higher education in Nigeria has eventually proved its relevance in the development of the nation's economic growth by enhancing creation of jobs and reducing youth employment in the Country to a point. Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria today has demonstrated that, it is a troll to improving the

economic situation, job creation and empowerment of Nigerians as this, which is a key driver of any economy, wealth and a high majority of jobs are created by small ventures started by entrepreneurially minded individuals, leading to the creation of big businesses, (Anho, 2014).

Entrepreneurship according to Ekpoh and Edet (2010) is the development of a business, starting with an idea and turning it into a profitable business. It is the journey of opportunity exploration and risk management to create value for profit and for social good. Uduak and Aniefiok (2011) also described entrepreneurship as the capacity and willingness to undertake venture with all attendant risks while seeking profit as a reward. Entrepreneurship is regarded as a key vehicle for employment creation, economic empowerment and an essential means of enhancing creativity and innovation that is dynamic in the local, regional and national economy (Agbakuru, 2012) Schumpeter cited in Ofoasia Nwalado (2010) opined that entrepreneurial process is a major factor in economic development and entrepreneurship is the key to economic growth. They further described entrepreneurship as an avenue of providing a satisfying and rewarding working life.

Due to the prevailing economic situation across the globe, policy makers have in recent time recognized entrepreneurship as instrument for economic emancipation which led to the integration of entrepreneurship education into the university education curriculum in providing the opportunity for undergraduates to acquire entrepreneurial knowledge, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship.

Following the presidential initiative to introduce entrepreneurship education in all tertiary institutions the federal government of Nigeria through the National Universities Commission resolved to introduce entrepreneurship education as a mandatory course for all Nigerian undergraduate students irrespective of their course of study.

Entrepreneurship education according to Aja-Okne (2000) and Adah (2013) is a specially training given to students to enable them acquire knowledge of business or financial risk, management abilities and capabilities of self-employment rather than being employed for pay. They further perceived. entrepreneurship education as one that prepare student to be responsible and enterprising so that they can attribute meaning to economic growth and development of the Country Ofuasia and Nwalado (2010), To Adebayo and Kolawole (2013) entrepreneurship education is the process of acquiring knowledge, special skill and experiences by an individual for effective adaptation to his environment. Entrepreneurship education seeks to equip students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings.

Entrepreneurship knowledge according to Chiaha and Agu (2013), Ademiluyi (2007) and Agbamu (2011) involves combining innovation, skills, and vision to develop new products, services, or ideal that meets market demand and creates value for a target audience. It is knowledge in a business capabilities and professional insight, which are develop and make use of in ones' business.

Entrepreneurship attitude as stated by Adebisi and Oni (2012) is the consistent behaviour and thinking, which are in line with creating and running a business. The desire of an individual to become an entrepreneur that precedes to become intention which forms the intention of a person to behave in certain manners.

Entrepreneurship skill education has been referred to as a source of employment generation because of its ability to enhance growth and development of a Country. This is why Adebayo and Kolawole (2013) asserted that entrepreneurship skill education is capable of making positive impacts on the economy of a nation and the quality of life of the people. Akhuemonkhan, Raimi and Sofoluwe (2013) in their study established that entrepreneurship skill education stimulates economic growth, generates employment and empowers the

disadvantaged segment of the population which include women and the poor.

Despite the monumental roles which entrepreneurship education is playing in providing the opportunity for student to gain the knowledge and acquire skills needed for starting up a new venture, joblessness among graduates in developing countries is still on the high side because only small percentage of the graduates that passed through entrepreneurship education general study became entrepreneur after graduation (Adeola and Bolarinwa, 2010).

Having discovered that government policy of entrepreneurship education integration into university education curriculum yield little result in creating entrepreneurship spirit, the question that may be asked is whether entrepreneurship education has equipped universities undergraduate with entrepreneurship education knowledge, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship in both private and public universities in Southwest Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship education has been receiving attention globally because of its importance to employment creation and economic growth. The introduction of entrepreneurship education general study in Nigeria universities is seen as a measure to address the problem of graduate unemployment and eradicate all forms of social vices. Entrepreneurship education has the mandate to equip the individual with functional knowledge and skill to build up their character, attitude and visions. Nevertheless, the training programme of entrepreneurship in developing countries like Nigeria has concentrated more on teaching knowledge and skills basically in principles. The products of these training are expected to be engaged in either self-employment or being employed. Unfortunately, Nigeria as a nation is characterized by high levels of graduates unemployment, poverty and different forms of social vices. It is on this note that this research study is designed to find out how Entrepreneurship education general study course has equipped university undergraduates with the Entrepreneurial knowledge change of

attitude to Entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in Entrepreneurship in South-west Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following were tested as 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the performance of university undergraduates in Entrepreneurial education in terms of:

- i. Entrepreneurship education knowledge
- ii. Change of attitude to entrepreneurship
- iii. Skills acquisition in entrepreneurship

H₀₂. There is no significance difference in the performance of university undergraduates from public and private universities in Entrepreneurship education in terms of:

- i. Entrepreneurship Knowledge acquisition
- ii. Change of attitude to entrepreneurship
- iii. Skills acquisition in entrepreneurship

Scope of the Study

The study was carryout in the South-west geographical zones of Nigeria, it comprises six states (Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo). The study will focus on the extent that entrepreneurship education general study course has equipped the undergraduate students with entrepreneurship education knowledge acquisition, skills acquisition and change of attitude to entrepreneurship in south western Nigerian universities. The study will also compare the extent at which the entrepreneurship education general study course has equipped students from public and private universities with necessary entrepreneurship education knowledge acquisition and change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skill acquisition in entrepreneurship.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will provide stakeholders in university education and entrepreneurial education with information regarding the extent to which entrepreneurial

education general studies course has equipped the undergraduates with entrepreneurship education knowledge, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in Entrepreneurship in South-west, Nigeria

Methodology

Research Design

To address the research problem, descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. This type of design was used because it is the most effective means of collecting data from a selected portion of the population from which the findings can later be generalized and because the study will not involve in the manipulation of variable but will depend on the existing data that will be obtained from undergraduate students.

Population of the Study

The target population for the study composed all three hundred level undergraduate students in all public and private universities in the south-western Nigeria who are currently offering entrepreneurship education general study course

Sampling Technique and Sample

The study employed multiple - stage sampling procedure.

Stage one South-west consists of six states (Lagos, Ondo, Ekiti, Osun, Ogun and Osun). The researchers used simple random sampling technique to select three out of six states. They used stratified sampling method to classify the universities into both public and private. The researcher also used simple random sampling technique in selecting a public and a private University from each of the three states and one was randomly selected and used in the pilot study.

Stage Two: The researcher used simple sampling technique to select six faculties from each university and the sample size of the current undergraduate students for the general study course of entrepreneurship education was proportionally chosen based on the total population of each faculty.

Table 1. Sampling Showing Framework of the Undergraduate Students in South-West Nigeria

State	Type of University	Total no of students	Total no of Sample used	Percentage (%)
Osun	O.A.U	5029	371	7.4
Osun	BOWEN	710	255	35.9
Ogun	O.O.U	4462	367	8.2
Ogun	BELLS	680	252	37.1
Ekiti	EKSU	4873	370	7.6
Ekiti	ABUAD	421	205	45.7
Total	06	16,175	1,820	11.3

Instrumentation

To provide information for the study, data were obtained using

1. Entrepreneurship Education Students' Achievement Test (EESAT)
2. Undergraduate Entrepreneurial and Managerial Competence Questionnaire (UEMCQ)

Entrepreneurial Education Students' Achievement Test (EESAT)

The EESAT constructed by the researchers was used as pre-test as well as post-test to determine the degree at which undergraduate students have acquired Entrepreneurial education knowledge. The instrument is made up of two sections A and B. Section A sought for students' personal data while Section B consisted of fifty multiple choice objective tests. Each test has one correct option which is the key and three distracters (A-D). The test was specifically drawn to cover six topics in Entrepreneurship education that are common in the sampled universities. These topics are: Meaning and scope of entrepreneurship education, creativity and innovation, feasibility study and Business plan, Business Organization, Risk Management in business, marketing and Business accounting. All the items of the test were constructed using Anderson and Krathwoh's (2001) taxonomy of educational objectives which were grouped into three levels, remembering, understanding and applying to validate the EEAT, a pool of fifty items was constructed and given to two experts in Test and measurement in the institute of Education, University of Ibadan, for their

suggestions and advice to ascertain that the test items have both face and content validity. The corrected version of the test items were eventually administered on one hundred undergraduates that were chosen from a university that was not part of the sample universities. The researchers computed the difficulty and discriminating indices by using a simplified item analysis table to select items that were neither too difficult nor too easy and which discriminate positively between the able and less able students. The number of items eventually survived the item analysis procedure constituted the EE students' Achievement Test. The reliability coefficient was determined using Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR-20) which gave 0.81 only twenty items out of 50 items that survived the trial testing were selected for the study.

Undergraduates' Entrepreneurial and Managerial Competence Questionnaire (UEMCQ)

The (UEMCQ) constructed by the researcher was used to collect information from the 300 level university undergraduate students of EE General Studies on their attitudes to entrepreneurship. The instrument consisted of two sections A - C. Section A sought demography information of the students; Section B: collected information on attitude of undergraduate students to Entrepreneurship before they are exposed to EE and after they might have been exposed to EE with 15 items placed beside the following response format: Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) while Section C collected information on students' entrepreneurial skills

acquisition in entrepreneurship on Creativity and Innovation with 11 items, Risk-Management with 9 items, Employment Generation with 6 items, Establishment of Career in SMEs with 6 items and Spirit of Perseverance with 5 items placed beside the following response format: Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Little Extent (LE) and Never (N). Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability and internal consistency which yielded coefficient of 0.72.

Data Collection Procedure

To carry out this study, the researchers trained six research assistants on the technicalities of how to administer the instruction. The researchers and research assistants visited all the sampled universities. The researchers obtained permission from the University before the administration of the instruments. Undergraduates' entrepreneurial managerial competence Questionnaire and entrepreneurship education student's Achievement Test-were administered on current entrepreneurship education general studies

course undergraduate students as pre-test before they were exposed to entrepreneurship education and pre-test after they have been exposed to entrepreneurship education.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data that were collected for the study were analysed with the use of inferential statistics (Paired and Independent T-Test). All data that were collected were analysed at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the performance of university undergraduates in EE in terms of:

- (i) Entrepreneurship education knowledge
- (ii) Change of attitude to entrepreneurship
- (iii) Skills acquisition in entrepreneurship?

Table 2. Performance of University Undergraduates in EE Students in South – West Nigeria which is the Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores in EE Student Achievement Test of Undergraduates in South-West Nigeria

Student's Performance	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	P-value	Remark
Student's Pre-test Score in EE	1820	22.34	15.13	337.26	1819	0.00	*S
Student's Post-test Score in EE	1820	42.34	15.14				

Note: *P< 0.05

The result in Table 2 shows the paired t-test that was used to compare difference in the acquisition of EE knowledge before and after the Undergraduates was exposed to EE General Study's course. There was significant difference ($t_{(1819)} = 337.26, p > 0.05$). The result revealed that there was significant different in the knowledge of EE before and after the teaching of EE. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld.

The result in Table 3 shows the differences in attitude of undergraduates towards entrepreneurship before and after they were exposed to EE. The result revealed that there was significant difference ($t_{(1819)} = 2400$) in pre-attitude and post attitudes of undergraduates towards entrepreneurship. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was upheld.

Table 3. The Comparison Between Pre-Attitude and Post-Attitude of Undergraduates Towards Entrepreneurship

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	p-value	Remarks
Pre-attitude towards EE	1820	22.34	2.88	2400.00	1819	0.00	*S
Post attitude towards EE	1820	42.34	42.88				

Note: *P<0.05

Table 4. Comparison of Undergraduate Students' Pre-Skills Acquisition and Post-Skills Acquisition in Entrepreneurship

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	P-value	Remarks
Pre-skills acquisition in EE	1820	47.85	5.46	12321.05	1819	0.00	*S
Post-skills acquisition in EE	1820	107.84	5.45				

Note: *P<0.05

The Table 4 above shows the differences in the entrepreneurship skills acquisition of undergraduates before and after they were exposed to EE General Study's course. The table revealed that there was significant difference ($t(1819) = 1232.80$) in entrepreneurship skills acquisition before and after they were exposed to EE General Studies course. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypothesis was upheld.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the performance of university undergraduate students from public and private universities in EE in terms of:

- (i) Entrepreneurship education knowledge acquisition
- (ii) Change of attitude to entrepreneurship
- (iii) Skills acquisition in entrepreneurship?

Table 5. Showing how EE-GSC has equipped the Students from Public and Private Universities with EE Knowledge, Change of Attitude to Entrepreneurship and Skills Acquisition in Entrepreneurship

Variables	School Ownership	Period	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Std. Error Mean	T	Df	Sig (p)
Students achievement	Public	Pre-test	1108	22.10	5.13	0.131	1.05	1819	0.991
	Private	Pre-test	712	20.21	5.15	0.309			
	Public	Post-test	1108	24.12	1.395	0.131	5.46	1819	0.000
	Private	Post-test	712	36.63	2.870	0.309			
Students attitude	Public	Pre-test	1108	22.28	2.87	0.730	1.98	1819	0.421
	Private	Pre-test	712	22.65	2.92	0.175			
	Public	Post-test	1108	30.61	2.073	0.138	4.96	1819	0.021
	Private	Post-test	712	31.07	1.859	0.329			
Students skill acquisition	Public	Pre-test	1108	47.62	5.42	0.138	2.21	1819	0.738
	Private	Pre-test	712	49.10	5.49	0.329			
	Public	Post-test	1108	107.62	5.42	0.138	4.20	1819	0.046
	Private	Post-test	712	109.10	5.49	0.329			

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference in the performance of university undergraduate students from public and private universities in terms of knowledge acquisition ($t=1.05$, $df=1819$, $p>0.05$), change of attitude to entrepreneurship ($t=1.98$, $df=1819$, $p>0.05$) and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship ($t=2.21$, $df=1819$, $p>0.05$) during the pre-test period. The table equally shows that there is significant difference in the performance of university undergraduate students from public and private universities in terms of knowledge acquisition ($t=5.460$, $df=1819$, $p<0.05$), change of attitude to entrepreneurship ($t=4.96$, $df=1819$, $p<0.05$) and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship ($t=4.20$, $df=1819$, $p<0.05$) at post-test level. The mean scores shows that undergraduate students from private universities achieved better than undergraduate students from public universities (undergraduate students from private universities=36.63, undergraduate students from public universities =24.12) in terms of knowledge acquisition. The results also shows that undergraduate students from private universities had better change of attitude to entrepreneurship than their counterparts who are from public universities (undergraduate students from private universities =31.07, undergraduate students from public universities =30.61). The undergraduate students from private universities had acquired better entrepreneurship skills than their counterparts in public universities (undergraduate students from private universities =109.10, undergraduate students from public universities =107.62).

Discussion

The result of hypothesis 1 revealed that there was significant difference in the knowledge of entrepreneurship education attitude to entrepreneurship and skills is in agreement with the findings of Uduak and Aniefiok (2011) who reports that entrepreneurship education add to students knowledge, disposition to entrepreneurship is likewise in accordance with the findings Agbim, Oriarewo and Owocho

(2013) that entrepreneurship education makes rousing attention to business opportunity and gives openness to entrepreneurship process, and provide information to undergraduates on method of establishing business venture. The finding additionally concurs with the findings of Ekpo and Edet (2011) entrepreneurship education impacts emphatically on the vocation of tertiary institution undergraduates. Therefore, entrepreneurship education increases undergraduates' knowledge of entrepreneurship, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship.

The result of hypothesis 2 showed that there is no significant difference in the performance of university undergraduate students from public and private universities in terms of knowledge acquisition, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship at pre-test level, where at post test level, the mean scores shows that undergraduate students from private universities achieved better than undergraduate students from public universities in terms of knowledge acquisition in entrepreneurship education, students from private universities had better change of attitude to entrepreneurship than their counterparts who are from public universities and the undergraduate students from private universities had acquisition better than their counterparts in public universities. This results is seeing as couldn't contradict the findings of Ezegebe, Eskay, and Anyanwu (2013) Agu and Yellowe (2013) Unachukwu (2009), Gibb (2009) Adragna and Lusari (2008) who revealed that school type influences the impacts of entrepreneurship education on students exposure to entrepreneurial intension, abilities and skills.

Summary of the Findings

1. Majority of the undergraduate students in the sampled universities have been equipped with the entrepreneurship education knowledge, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship.

2. There is no significant different in the performance of university undergraduate students from public and private university in term of entrepreneurship education knowledge acquired change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquired in entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

The study assessed the entrepreneurship education knowledge acquisition, change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in entrepreneurship. Also the course has equipped the beneficiary from both private and public university the entrepreneurship knowledge change of attitude to entrepreneurship and skills acquisition in Entrepreneurship the same way.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following were recommended.

1. University lecturers should demonstrate a strong dedication to the teaching of entrepreneurship education general studies.
2. Government, non-governmental organizations and philanthropists should assist in providing sufficient resources for the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education general studies course.
3. The Vice Chancellors in Public Universities should intensify more efforts on effective implementation of entrepreneurship education general studies course.
4. Motivation should be introduced by the Nigeria government and university Vice Chancellors to both the students and the lecturers for effective teaching and learning of entrepreneurship in both Private and Public Universities.

References

Adebayo, O. & Kolawole, J.A (2013). The Historical Background of Entrepreneurship

development in Nigeria: Its Gains, Shortcoming and Needful. *Journal of emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 4(50), 493-500.

Adebisi, T.A. & Oni, C.S. (2012). Assessment of relevance of National Directorate of Employment training programme to the needs of the trainees in south-west in Nigeria. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 4(3), 29-37. <https://doi.org/10.5897/IJVTE11.034>

Ademiluyi, L.F. (2007) Business competences needed for effective entrepreneurship as perceived by fresh graduate. *Business Journal*, 1(1), 18-29.

Adeola, K.L & Bolarinwa, K. (2010). Strategies for promoting entrepreneurship education in secondary school curriculum. *Business Education Journal*, 1(10), 221-227

Adragna, S. & Lusardi, A. (2008), *Explaining International Differences in Entrepreneurship: The Role of Individual Characteristics and Regulatory Constraint*. National Bureau of Economic Research, Working Paper.

Agbakuru J. (2012). *Why unemployment will increase*. Vanguard Daily 26 November.

Agbamu, T.P. (2011). Approaches Considered Effective for Teaching Entrepreneurship in Business Education. *Business Education Journal*, 8(1), 23-32

Agbim, K.C., Oriarewo, G.O., & Owocho, M. (2013). Factors influencing Entrepreneurial intention among Graduates of Nigerian Tertiary Institution. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(4), 36-44.

Agi, U.K. & Yellowe, N.A (2013). Management Strategies for Regenerating Secondary education for National Development and Self-Reliance. *Journal of Teacher Perspective*, 7(2), 1-12.

Agbonlahor A.A (2016) Challenges of entrepreneurial education in Nigeria universities: Toward a Repositioning for impact. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 6(1), 208-214. <https://doi.org/10.5901/JESR.2016.V6N1P208>

- Agu, C.N. (2006). Pedagogy of Entrepreneurship in A Contemporary Society. *The Enterprise International Research Journal for Development*, 8(1), 18-32. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(99\)00042-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(99)00042-7)
- Aja-Okorie, U. & Adali, O. (2013). Achieving Youth Empowerment through Repositioning Entrepreneurial Education in education in Nigeria Universities: Problem. *Prospects European Scientific Journal*, 3, (9), 2-8.
- Akhuemonkhan, I.A, Raimi, L. & Sofoluwe, A. (2013). Entrepreneurship Education and Employment Stimulation in Nigeria. *Journal of Studies in Social Science*, 3(1), 55-79.
- Anho, J.E. (2011). Impact of Entrepreneurship Education and Training on University Graduates for Sustainable Development in E.A. Arubayi, N.E. Akpotu and E.P. Oghuvbu (Eds.) *A Book of Reading: Education and Training for Entrepreneurship*.
- Anho, J. E. (2014). Entrepreneurship education: A panaces for unemployment, poverty reduction and national unity in developing and underdeveloped country American, *International Journal of contemporary Research*, 4(3).
- Aladekomo F.O. (2004) Nigeria Educational Policy and Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Social Science*, 9(2), 75-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2004.11892434>
- Arogundade, B.B. (2011). Entrepreneurship Education: An Imperative for Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 2(1), 26-29.
- Chiaha, G. T. U. & Agu, R. A. (2013). *Business venture, schooling and graduate employ ability in Nigeria: An examination proposition introduced at Association of African Universities*. AAU.
- Cooney, T. (2009), What Entrepreneurship Skills are Important to Innovation in SMEs and How Should They be Promoted through Policy? Paper Presented to *OECD Conference on SMEs, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Udine, Italy*.
- Egai (2009) Entrepreneur skill development and economic development in Nigeria. Paper presented at a *seminar organized by the institute of chartered Economist of Nigerian*, held on 10th July, at center for Women Development Central Area, Abuja, FCT.
- Ekpo, U.I. & Edet, A.O. (2011). Entrepreneurial education and career intention of tertiary education student in Akwa-ibom and Cross-River States, Nigeria. *Journal of International Education Studies*, 4(1), 172-178. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v4n1p172>
- Ekpoh, U.I. & Edet, A.O. (2011). Entrepreneurship Education and Career Intentions of Tertiary Education Students in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria. *International Education Studies*, 4(1), 172
- Ekwubara, M.U. (2010). Strategies for promoting Entrepreneurship education (NCE) home economics. *Journal of Higher Educational Research*, 137-143
- Ezegbe, B.N., Eskay, M. & Anyanwu, J. (2013). Poverty alleviation among Nigeria youth via entrepreneurial education: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(14), 97-101.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- NUC. (2011). *Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards for Graduate Programmes in Nigerian Universities*. Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship.
- Gibb, A. (2009), The Small Business and Entrepreneurship Challenges to Vocational Education: Revolution or Evolution? A paper Presented at *OECD Conference on SMEs, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Udine, Italy*.
- Harvey, L. & Morey, A. (2002), *Enhancing employability: recognizing diversity: making links between higher education and the world of work*. Universities UK and CSU.
- Idogho, P.O. & Akhigbe, O.J. (2012). Responsive Curriculum Development in Business Education Challenges and Implication. *Association of Business Education Book of Readings*, 2(1), 261-267.

- Mensah, J. (2019). Sustainable development: meaning, history principle pillars, and implications for human action: a literature review. *Cogent social sciences*, 5(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2019.1653531>
- Ofuasia, J.N., & Nwalado, E.N. (2010). Entrepreneurship Education for Youth Employment in Nigeria: Implication for Social Studies Education. *European Journal of Social Science*, 15(1), 146-50.
- Olayinka, C. (2010). *Turkey to partner on Job Creation in Initiations*. Lagos: The Guardian Newspaper.
- Olise, I.M. (2011). Entrepreneurship Development through Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. *Business Education Book of Readings*, 1(II), 123-124.
- Okon, F.I (2002). *Strategies for Improving Student Interest in Accounting in Secondary Schools Akwa Ibom State*. Unpublished.
- Uduak, M.E. & Aniefiok, O.E (2011). Entrepreneurship Education and Career Intentions of Tertiary Education. *International Education Studies*, 4(1), 172-178. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v4n1p172>
- Unachukwu, G.O. (2009). Issues and Challenges in the Development of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*, 3(5), 213-226. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/afrrrev.v3i5.51153>